

ESTABLISHMENT OF A BURIAL SITE REGISTRY

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Abstract: *In order to improve service provision, better resource management, and utilization in communal activities of particular public interest, such as funeral services, records are necessary. In the Republic of Srpska, there are legislative provisions regarding records of funeral services that have been analyzed for the purposes of this study. By employing unmanned aerial vehicle surveys, it is possible to obtain accurate data in a relatively short time frame, and by linking this with databases, up-to-date records are obtained. Through research and the practical part of the study, it has been demonstrated that maintaining records in databases and linking them with graphical representations provide a much clearer and more comprehensive picture of the situation on the ground, as well as offer various possibilities for planned development and expansion of cemeteries.*

Keywords: *Burial site, Cemetery, Unmanned aerial vehicles, Orthophoto, Database.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Records of land date back to the Roman Empire when tax assessment registers existed, continuing to the present day where cadastral records represent a collection of data about land and the objects on it (Miladinović Manojlo, 2013). Land data is utilized for statistical, economic, and various other purposes, as well as for maintaining diverse records. With the advancement of science and technology, there emerged a need for utilizing databases in cadastral systems, aiming to refine record-keeping across different domains. The demand for various land records is increasing, leading to the development of cadastres in fields such as geology, ecology, transportation, agriculture, forestry, mining, construction, and others. In order to enhance services, and improve resource management, and utilization, records are required in communal activities of particular public interest, such as funeral services.

In the Republic of Srpska, legislative provisions exist pertaining to records in funeral services (Official Gazette of the City of Banja Luka, 2013; Law on Cemeteries and Funeral Services, 2014), and with the advancement of technology, the utilization of databases and software packages for graphical representation enables the enhancement of such records. The demand in this field and urban planning indicates the necessity to analyze, assess, and establish unified methodologies for cemetery documentation, as well as the need for organized management, coordination, and direction of activities in this sector. Through new surveying methods, it is possible to obtain accurate data in a relatively short time frame, and by linking this with databases, up-to-date records are obtained (Barrile et al., 2020; BUZNA et al., 2021; Rahardjo et al., 2020).

The cemetery cadastre contains data on graves, burial sites for urns, owners of burial sites and graves, individuals entitled to burial rights, as well as all changes and causes of death. An integral part of this record is the positional plan of burial sites and graves (Law on Cemeteries, 2017). This type of cadastral record exists in countries within the region, such as Croatia (*Cemeteries*, 2022), as well as in other countries like Austria and Germany (*Friedhöfe Wien*, 2022)

Researchers have long recognized the need to integrate IT and geodetic methods to create a record that allows for real-time monitoring and regulation of funeral services. Works (Coruhlu et al., 2021; IEVSIUKOV et al., 2022; Mohamad et al., 2023; Schmidt, 2018) describe the use of geographic information

systems in terms of their application for management, site selection, and intelligent management and manipulation of funeral service systems.

Conducting a survey of a cemetery and recording burial sites from the ground requires significant time and money, especially for large areas. An alternative to this is aerial digitization of the cemetery. Using a high-resolution camera-equipped drone, cemeteries can be captured in detail from a high altitude. Thanks to preserved, precise geospatial data for each image, a digital cemetery cadastre can be created. Data captured in a relatively short time frame, which is highly accurate, can be imported into cemetery management software, used for managing graves, and retrieved from the database at any time (Unger et al., 2017).

The creation of a record and visualization that provides users with all necessary information is the starting point of this study. Emphasis is placed on using the QGIS software package to display data, with data being stored in a PostgreSQL database. Various queries in the database and the QGIS software package should display attributes related to burial sites such as site number, owner, area, or the individual buried. Practical examples will be conducted on orthophotos of the city cemetery at Pobrđe and the cemetery at Vrbanja.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Area of interest

The burial site cadastre was prepared for the city cemetery at Pobrđe and the cemetery at Vrbanja, both located in the city of Banja Luka, as depicted in Figure 1. The city cemetery at Pobrđe covers an area of approximately 83500 m², while the city cemetery at Vrbanja occupies an area of around 31088 m². The cemetery situated at Pobrđe location encompasses multiple cadastral parcels, namely parcels 32, 35, 36, 38, 39, 40, and 41, whereas the cemetery located at Vrbanja is situated on a single parcel, parcel number 677/1.

Figure 1: Area of interest.

2.2. Input data

The images of the surveyed areas were captured by an unmanned aerial vehicle – the Ruide Drone-eco Pro, by a surveying company. The survey was conducted in April 2022. The Ruide Drone-eco Pro model features a body with four foldable propellers arranged in an X-shaped configuration. The drone is fully integrated and ready to use without the need for assembly, with the capability of vertical takeoff and landing. The maximum length of the device diagonally is 716 mm, and the dimensions of the device are 564 x 564 x

360 mm (length, width, height). The weight of the device with the battery is 5.15 kg, and without the battery, it is 2.35 kg. The maximum payload capacity of the drone is 1.4 kg, making the maximum takeoff weight 6.55 kg. The positioning accuracy of the device is 1 cm + 1 ppm horizontally and 1.5 cm + 1 ppm vertically. With a single flight, an area of up to 6 km² can be surveyed.

For the processing needs, 188 terrain images of the central city cemetery at Vrbanja and 125 terrain images of the cemetery at Pobrđe are utilized.

The Law on Cemeteries and Funeral Services (Law on Cemeteries and Funeral Services, 2014) defines the fundamental concepts relevant to the development of the database, and a schema has been devised based on which tables and data types are created in the database.

2.3. Methods

The cemetery cadastre database creation is performed using the pgAdmin 4 tool, which serves to manage the open-source PostgreSQL database worldwide (Drake & Worsley, 2002).

Processing of images obtained by the unmanned aerial vehicle was conducted in the Agisoft Metashape software, which performs photogrammetric processing of digital images, captured by RGB or multispectral cameras, including multi-camera systems. It generates 3D spatial data and enables image processing into spatial information in the form of dense point clouds, polygon models with textures, georeferenced orthomosaics, digital surface models, and digital elevation models (*Agisoft Metashape User Manual Professional Edition, Version 1.7, 2021*). Further post-processing allows for shadow and texture removal from the model, vegetation index calculation, extraction of information for interactive maps, automatic classification of dense point clouds, and more.

After processing the terrain images, orthomosaics for both cemeteries are loaded into QGIS as raster layers. Additionally, the PostgreSQL database created is linked to QGIS. Upon integrating the database and orthomosaics, geometric elements of the cemetery are delineated, and database tables are populated. Real data were not used for populating the database tables for the study due to the fact that the enterprise "City Cemetery Banja Luka" possesses such data and, for privacy reasons, did not consent to their usage.

2.3.1. Database creation

The schema comprises seven tables and five data types. The tables are intended to contain basic information about the cemetery, burial site, grave, individuals buried or entitled to burial, and ownership. During table population, the type of cemetery can be selected based on surface area and burial method, cemetery type according to purpose, cemetery administration, as well as the legal basis for acquiring ownership of the burial site. The schema was developed in accordance with the Law on Cemeteries and Funeral Services (Law on Cemeteries and Funeral Services, 2014), as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schema of database creation in Serbian language.

2.3.2. Image processing obtained by an unmanned aerial vehicle

Image processing obtained by an unmanned aerial vehicle was conducted using Agisoft Metashape software. The first stage of image processing is carried out by the command Workflow - Align Photos, which

improves the camera position for each photograph. In the second phase, aerotriangulation is performed with greater accuracy. If the Reference option is enabled, the overlap between photographs is predicted based on the geolocation of the photographs. Aerotriangulation is performed only with overlapping photographs. Agisoft Metashape enables the creation and visualization of dense point clouds. The point cloud generation is based on the estimated camera locations, and the generated point cloud has nearly the same density as the point cloud generated using LiDAR technology. The process is initiated by Workflow - Build Dense Cloud.

A Digital Elevation Model (DEM) is a digital representation of the terrain surface, i.e., it is a 2.5D surface model represented in the form of a regular grid, with height values for each grid point (Balasubramanian, 2017). Metashape allows the creation of this model via the command Workflow - Build DEM. With the interpolation mode enabled, Metashape will compute DEM for all areas visible in at least one image, and the setting is recommended for generating DEM.

An orthomosaic is a combined image created by merging original images projected onto the object surface and transforming into the selected projection, while an orthophoto projection is an individual image projected onto the object surface and transformed into the selected projection. Thus, an orthomosaic is created by merging orthophotos (*Agisoft Metashape User Manual Professional Edition, Version 1.7, 2021*).

Creating a high-resolution orthomosaic based on existing photographs and reconstructed terrain: Workflow - Build Orthomosaic. For the Surface parameter, it is recommended to use DEM, while for more demanding applications, DSM is used, and the Blend mode is set to Mosaic.

The orthomosaic of a part of the Vrbanja cemetery, obtained by processing photographs, was exported in .tiff format, and its appearance can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The orthomosaic of a part of the cemetery at Vrbanja.

2.3.3. Integration into QGIS

After the terrain image processing, orthomosaics for both cemeteries are loaded into QGIS as raster layers. After the raster layers are loaded, they are connected to the database. After the connection is established, layers with geometry in the database are created.

The tables are populated in pgAdmin 4 either directly or through code:

```
INSERT INTO table_name (column_1, column_2, column_3 ...)
```

```
VALUES (value 1, value 2, value 3...);
```

3. RESULTS

As a result of database creation, image processing, and polygon drawing, a comprehensive record of burial sites with graphical representation is obtained. This allows for the search and display of available and occupied burial plots, associated individuals, and other related data stored in tables. The integration of data and graphics provides a clearer understanding of the current situation on the ground, serving as a basis for needs assessment, planning for cemetery expansion, and landscape development.

Various tools are available in pgAdmin 4 for viewing existing data. One method involves creating a view using SQL code, which consolidates relevant data from multiple tables into a single virtual table.

To display occupied and vacant burial sites, the tables `burial_site2` (`grobno_mjesto2`) and `grave2` (`grob2`) need to be joined. If the primary key from `burial_site2` exists in the `grave2` table, the site is considered occupied, and the corresponding column in the view is assigned the value 1. If the primary key is not found in `grave2`, the site is vacant, and the value is set to 0. Other attributes from both tables can also be selected and included in the view.

If there is no need to retain the displayed data permanently, a temporary table can be used instead.

In addition to viewing data in pgAdmin 4, the same data can be visualized in QGIS. A layer is added using the created view `grobna_mjesta_zauzeto2`. By right-clicking on the layer and selecting Layer

Properties, then navigating to the Symbology tab, the Categorized option can be chosen from the dropdown menu. The classification is based on the occupied column from the view, which contains two values (0 and 1), as defined in pgAdmin 4. This classification is now displayed visually in the QGIS interface, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The depiction of available and occupied burial sites in QGIS.

QGIS also enables table joins, allowing the display of all necessary attributes in a single view. Using the Join option, the tables `grob2`, `grob_osoba2`, and `osoba2` can be associated with `grobno_mjesto2`. All columns from the joined tables are then available in the attribute table. During the join process, QGIS allows you to choose which columns to include. Once the joins are complete and attributes are added, the information can be visualized graphically.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

From the time when land records were used for tax collection to the present day, where cadastral surveys represent a comprehensive record containing data about land and objects on it, significant advancements in technology, data collection methods, and record-keeping can be observed. Once, cemeteries were merely marked on maps with specific topographic symbols, but today, with appropriate computer software, electronic records can be maintained, and data can be linked with graphics.

Following the analysis of legal regulations for the practical part of the study, deficiencies were identified regarding the definition of the term "grave chamber" and the condominium of burial sites. The concept of a grave chamber is not defined either in the Law on Cemeteries and Funeral Services or in the Decision of the City of Banja Luka, thus, it is not clear what is meant by this term. Therefore, it would be necessary to eliminate ambiguities regarding this concept in terms of its meaning and determining the number of individuals who need to and can be buried, so that the land area can be called a grave chamber. Subsequently, this term could be added to the database itself, enabling an even more advanced review of cemetery records.

In practice, it happens that multiple individuals are buried in one burial site. The Law on Cemeteries and Funeral Services does not define the condominium of burial sites, while Article 43 of the Decision of the City of Banja Luka defines that a maximum of two individuals can be buried in one grave if a grave chamber has not been previously built. Since the concept of a grave chamber is unclear, and the number of individuals that can be buried is unknown, this Decision also does not clearly define the number of individuals that can be buried in one burial site or grave chamber. Therefore, the allowed number of condominiums when creating the database could not be defined.

The Regulation on the Content and Manner of Maintaining Cemetery Records provided for by the Law on Cemeteries and Funeral Services has not been adopted, so the Cemetery Administration maintains records in accordance with this Law, which was considered for the practical part of the study. To improve record-keeping, it would be necessary to develop the Regulation on the Content and Manner of Maintaining Cemetery Records.

With the introduction of the Regulation on the Content and Manner of Maintaining Cemetery Records, all records would be aligned, avoiding individual interpretation of the Law by each Cemetery Administration regarding the data kept in the records, data presentation, and search methods, and the appearance of the

records themselves, which should be clear and concise, enabling necessary information checks for buyers or visitors.

Survey methods for data collection demonstrate significant progress in terms of equipment and terrain recording methods. Today, it is possible to quickly and efficiently produce survey maps with satisfactory accuracy. This study shows that the method of recording data with unmanned aerial vehicles is a suitable solution for these purposes. After processing the images, an orthophoto is obtained, which can be used as a basis for a graphical representation of cemeteries and burial sites.

By using specific software packages, images obtained from unmanned aerial vehicle surveys can be processed, and an orthophoto can be obtained. Further use of software packages digitizes this base and links it with a database. In this way, various queries can be created, making data search faster and simpler.

The application of new terrain survey methods yields results of satisfactory accuracy, and data is collected relatively quickly. Maintaining records in databases and linking them with graphics provides a much clearer and more transparent picture of the situation on the ground, offering various possibilities for planned development and expansion of cemeteries. Buyers can more easily access information about available sites, while visitors can more easily locate the graves of family members.

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